

Two new species of the genus *Moitessieria* (Gastropoda, Moitessieriidae) from Spain

Dos nuevas especies del género *Moitessieria* (Gastropoda, Moitessieriidae) de España

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ABSTRACT

Two new species of the genus *Moitessieria* from the autonomous community of Catalonia are described. They were found respectively in sediments from springs in Vilanova de Meià (Lleida) and in Sant Feliu de Pallerols (Girona). The new species are compared with other congeneric species from which they conchologically differ.

RESUMEN

Se describen dos nuevas especies del género *Moitessieria* procedentes de la comunidad autónoma de Cataluña. Se han hallado en sedimentos de una fuente en Vilanova de Meià (Lleida) y de Sant Feliu de Pallerols (Girona). Las nuevas especies son comparadas con otras especies congénéricas con las cuales se diferencian conquiliológicamente.

INTRODUCTION

The family Moitessieriidae Bourguignat, 1883 is represented by freshwater species of stygobiotic habitat, small size and semi-translucent shell, spiral ornamentation and, in most of the cases, a high number of whorls. In Spain, this family is represented by five genera, from which the genus *Moitessieria* Bourguignat, 1863 is present by different species distributed in Catalonia, Valencian Community, Aragon and Navarra. (ALTIMIRA, 1960; BOETERS, 2003; CORBELLA ET AL. 2006, 2011, 2012; ALBA ET AL. 2011, 2013; TARRUELLA ET AL. 2012, 2013, 2015).

In the present work, two new species of this genus are described for Catalonia, which differ in their conchological characteristics from other congeneric species already described.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The shells of the species here described were collected from sediment and shell grit. *Moitessieria hedraensis* n. sp. was obtained from material collected in the Font de l'Hedra, in Vilanova de Meià, province of Lleida (10-7-2014, SQS col.) and *Moitessieria garrotxaensis* n. sp. was collected in the Font de la Teula, in Sant Feliu de Pallerols, province of Girona (26-12-2015, SQS col.).

The sieves used for sorting the sediment were 2 mm, 1 mm and 0.5 mm, the shells were then separated under a stereomicroscope for their determination. They were cleaned with water using a small brush.

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Abbreviations
MNCN Museo Nacional de Ciencias
Naturales, Madrid

MZB Museu de Ciències Naturals de
Barcelona.
CSQ Collection Sergio Quiñonero

SYSTEMATICS

Family MOITESSIERIIDAE Bourguignat, 1883

Genus *Moitessieria* Bourguignat, 1863

Type species: *Paludina simoniana* Saint-Simon, 1848.

Moitessieria hedraensis n. sp. (Figure 1A-G, 3 A-E)

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 1A) in MZB 2017-0449; paratype (Fig. 1B) in MNCN 15.05/200002. CSQ: 5 shells (Figure 3A-E).

Type locality: Font de l'Hedra, Vilanova de Meià, 680 m, comarca de La Noguera, province of Lleida [31TCG35]. (Figure 4A)

Etymology: The specific name refers to the fountain where the new species was collected.

Description: Shell small (<2 mm), of conical-turriculate form, fragile, translucent, a little glossy, with 3 to 4 whorls, uniformly convex and with a well marked suture.

The protoconch has about two whorls, a nucleus of about 90 μm , a maximum diameter of about 320 μm and a height of about 300 μm . All the protoconch shows a very delicate microsculpture formed by about 10 fine spirals bands in which some small rounded or somewhat elongated elevations can be seen, with smooth spaces between them and, occasionally, some smooth areas in the suprasutural zone.

The teleoconch presents a sculpture of about 13-15 narrow bands, which at their upper part are slightly detached and appear to have a cutting edge, while at the lower part are covered by the band located below. In subsutural areas, the upper edge of these bands seems to be somehow more serrated and there are small axial threads separating small, somewhat depressed pits. In other areas, under high magnification, there are numerous growth lines. The pits delimited by the axial threads become more conspicuous on the later teleoconch whorls, and on the last whorl, these are present over almost its entire surface.

Aperture ovoid, slightly irregular, a little narrower in its upper part, the

columella is detached from a narrow umbilicus. The parietal area is thin and adherent with the last whorl. The aperture is smooth inside.

Dimensions: The holotype has a height of 1.25 mm and a width of 0.65 mm; see Table I for further measurements.

Habitat: Stygobiotic. No live material was found. The shells were transported by the water current.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality.

Remarks: The main feature of the present species is a relatively low height and a rather conical form. The known species which have more similarity with this new species are:

Moitessieria foui Boeters, 2003 is slightly larger, the whorls are more convex, the umbilicus broader, its protoconch has a 1½ whorls, the microsculpture of its protoconch is formed by about 15 bands similar to those described in the new species, but separated by very fine spiral cordlets. The sculpture of the teleoconch is formed by finer and numerous bands, which have depressions that tend to finish towards the upper part in a prominent but rounded peak. The aperture is expanded outwards (BOETERS, 2003; ALBA ET AL., 2013).

Moitessieria juvenisanguis Boeters & Gittenberger, 1980, is also slightly larger,

Figure 1. *Moitessieria hedraensis* n. sp. A: holotype (MZB 2017-0449), 1.25 mm, Font de l'Hedra, Vilanova de Meià; B: paratype (MNCN 15.05/200002), 1.15 mm, from the type locality; C: apex and protoconch of the holotype; D, E: microsculpture of the protoconch and detail of the paratype; F, G: microsculpture of the teleconch and detail.

Figura 1. Moitessieria hedraensis n. sp. A: holotipo (MZB 2017-0449), 1,25 mm, Font de l'Hedra, Vilanova de Meià; B: paratipo (MNCN 15.05/200002), 1,15 mm, de la localidad tipo; C: ápice y protoconcha del holotipo; D, E: microescultura de la protoconcha y detalle de un paratipo; F, G: microescultura de la teleconcha y detalle.

more robust, its last whorl more convex, the umbilicus is broader, the peristome is incurved towards outside, and the sinus of the upper part of the umbilicus

is very pronounced. In addition, the microsculpture of the protoconch is very different (see CORBELLA ET AL., 2011, fig. 9).

Moitessieria garrotxaensis n. sp. (Figure 2A-G, 3 F-J)

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 2 A-B) in MZB 2017-0450, paratypes in in MNCN 15.05/200003. CSQ: 5 shells (Figure 3F-J).

Type locality: Font de la Teula, Sant Feliu de Pallerols, 470 m, comarca de la Garrotxa, Girona. [31TDG55]. (Figure 4B)

Etymology: The specific name refers to the Garrotxa county, where the spring of the type locality is located.

Description: Shell small (about 2 mm), elongated, subcylindrical, fragile, translucent, a little shiny, with 6-7 whorls, uniformly convex and with a well marked suture.

The protoconch has about 1.2-1.4 whorls, with a height of about 270 μ m and a diameter of about 360 μ m. Its surface appears smooth, but under high magnification numerous spiral lines formed by small tubercles can be seen. Near the end of the protoconch the number of these tubercles decreases, and the spiral lines are smooth or nearly smooth.

Teleoconch with about 5-6 whorls also with a smooth aspect, although under high magnification it can be seen as covered by very fine spiral cordlets, 20-28 in the last whorl. Umbilicus very narrow. Aperture ovoid, slightly narrower in its upper part, with a marked adapical sinus. Outer lip slightly flaring, parietal area thin and adherent to the last whorl above the columella.

Dimensions: The holotype has a height of 2.2 mm and a width of 0.72 mm; see Table II for further measurements.

Habitat: Stygobiotic. Not alive material was found. The shells were transported by the water current.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality.

Remarks: Some congeneric species of the region have an apparent similarity:

Moitessieria sanctichristophori Corbella *et al.*, 2011, has the whorls slightly higher, the shell is smaller and the sculpture of the teleoconch is formed by chains of almost rectangular depressions.

Moitessieria ollerii Altimira, 1960 has a subconical shell, slightly larger (it can reach 2.5 mm), but with more elongated whorls. For a similar size (of about 2 mm) this last species has an additional whorl. Umbilicus reduced to a narrow fissure or not existing. The microsculpture of the protoconch has an irregular appearance with very faint spiral striae barely noticeable even with high magnification. The spiral striation of the teleoconch is much more numerous (from 30 to 40 spiral striae).

Moitessieria mugae Corbella Alonso *et al.*, 2006 has similar dimensions, but the whorls are a bit higher, especially the last one, the umbilicus is reduced to a narrow fissure, the peristoma is simple, without any eversion, and the microsculpture of the protoconch lacks tubercles.

Moitessieria tatirocae Tarruella *et al.*, 2015 has a shell slightly larger (up to 2.5 mm) and can reach up to 10 spiral whorls. The umbilicus is reduced to a narrow fissure. The microsculpture of the protoconch is irregular, formed by scarce lines and tubercles, spirally oriented. The microsculpture of the teleoconch is formed by spirally aligned depressions.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Two new species of Moitessieridae, *Moitessieria hedraensis* n. sp. and *Moitessieria garrotxaensis* n. sp., are described for Catalonia (NE Spain) on the base of their conchological characteristics (Figures 1, 2, 3, Tables I, II).

They can be safely distinguished from some other species inhabiting the closest areas by their distinctive morphology.

With these two new species, 25 *Moitessieria* species are already described for

Figure 2. *Moitessieria garrotxaensis* n. sp. A, B: holotype (MZB 2017-0450), 2.2 mm, Font de la Teula, Sant Feliu de Pallerols (Girona); C: paratype (MNCN 15.05/200003) 2.0 mm, from the type locality; D, E: protoconch of the holotype and detail; F, G: microsculpture of the teleoconch and detail.

Figura 2. Moitessieria garrotxaensis n. sp. A, B: *holotipo* (MZB 2017-0450), 2.2 mm, Font de la Teula, Sant Feliu de Pallerols (Girona); C: *paratipo* (MNCN 15.05/200003) 2,0 mm, de la localitat tip; D, E: *protoconcha* del holotipo y detalle; F, G: *microescultura* de la teleoconcha y detalle.

Spain. Future research in springs will likely increase this number, given the high number of recently described new

species, and their usual limited range of distribution and high degree of endemism.

Table I. Measurements of the shell of *Moitessieria hedraensis* n. sp. Min: minimum; Mx: maximum; AV: average; SD: standard deviation; COEF. VAR: variance coefficient; L: length; D: diameter; Ha: aperture height; Wa: aperture width.

Tabla I. Mediciones de la concha de *Moitessieria hedraensis* n. sp. Min: mínimo; Mx: máximo; AV: media; SD: desviación estándar; COEF. VAR: coeficiente de variación; L: longitud; D: diámetro; Ha: altura de la abertura; Wa: anchura de la abertura.

N=10	Min	Mx	AV	SD	COEF. VAR.
L	1.07	1.34	1.157	0.088	0.076
D	0.64	0.71	0.666	0.031	0.046
Ha	0.42	0.61	0.509	0.051	0.101
Wa	0.39	0.46	0.421	0.021	0.050

Table II. Measurements of the shell of *Moitessieria garrotxaensis* n. sp. Min: minimum; Mx: maximum; AV: average; SD: standard deviation; COEF. VAR: variance coefficient; L: length; D: diameter; Ha: aperture height; Wa: aperture width.

Tabla II. Mediciones de la concha de *Moitessieria garrotxaensis* n. sp. Min: mínimo; Mx: máximo; AV: media; SD: desviación estándar; COEF. VAR: coeficiente de variación; L: longitud; D: diámetro; Ha: altura de la abertura; Wa: anchura de la abertura.

N=10	Min	Mx	AV	SD	COEF. VAR.
L	1.86	2.23	2.021	0.150	0.074
D	0.61	0.86	0.691	0.074	0.107
Ha	0.42	0.54	0.477	0.033	0.069
Wa	0.37	0.44	0.397	0.024	0.060

Figure 3. A-E: *Moitessieria hedraensis* n. sp., paratypes from the type locality. F-J: *Moitessieria garrotxaensis* n. sp., paratypes from the type locality.

Figura 3. A-E: *Moitessieria hedraensis* n. sp., paratipos de la localidad tipo. F-J: *Moitessieria garrotxaensis* n. sp., paratipos procedentes de la localidad tipo.

Figure 4. Habitats where the new species were collected. A: Font de l'Hedra, Vilanova de Meià. (*Moitessieria hedraensis* n. sp.); B: Font de la Teula, Sant Feliu de Pallerols (*Moitessieria garrotxaensis* n. sp.).
Figura 4. Hàbitats donde fueron recolectadas las nuevas especies. A: Font de l'Hedra, Vilanova de Meià. (*Moitessieria hedraensis* n. sp.); B: Font de la Teula, Sant Feliu de Pallerols (*Moitessieria garrotxaensis* n. sp.).

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